

A macroeconomic analysis of Zambia's Integrated Resource Planning

SAM multiplier analysis of electricity
investments

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Version 2

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Summary

The Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) provides a comprehensive roadmap to 2050 required to meet Zambia's projected electricity demand while supporting Zambia's broader development ambitions. To implement the IRP, significant levels of investment will need to be mobilised, in the order of USD25 billion. Whilst an ambitious plan of investment, the IRP could also bring benefits to the wider economy. In this paper, we undertake a SAM-based Multiplier Analysis to assess the wider economic benefits of the IRP.

We find that the macroeconomic benefits are considerable from the proposed IRP investments. For every unit of capital injected into the energy sector, it generates nearly double its value in gross output, while simultaneously expanding national value-added (GDP) by 10 percent beyond the initial investment. Furthermore, the vast majority (87%) of the economic expansion induced by the IRP investment is retained within the Zambian economy.

A key question is whether the IRP can fully achieve its intended inclusive growth objectives. The distributional results indicate that economic gains are likely to be concentrated in sectors and households that are already well integrated into formal economic activities, while rural households and urban lower-income groups capture a smaller share of the benefits. Further policy interventions are therefore likely to be needed to realise broader based benefits.

To realise these broader benefits, a number of interventions and enabling conditions are needed. These include strengthening domestic supply chains, promoting productive uses of electricity in rural areas, enhancing local participation in energy infrastructure development, and supporting sectors with strong employment and income linkages.

Introduction

Zambia maintains the ambition to transform its economy and attain middle-income status, as articulated in Vision 2030 (GRZ, 2006). Central to this transformation is the energy sector, which serves as a critical enabler. To meet this objective, the sector must expand significantly while simultaneously minimising emissions, ensuring security of supply, and achieving universal energy access. These development priorities are exemplified in the National Development Plans and, for the power sector, the Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) for the Power Sector in Zambia (MoE, 2024).

The IRP represents a comprehensive, long-term least-cost roadmap to 2050 required to meet Zambia's projected electricity demand while supporting Zambia's broader development ambitions. This is largely driven by accelerated industrialisation and Government's ambitious mining target of 3 million tonnes of copper per annum. While previous academic work, such as the "Greening the Recovery" analysis (Nyambe-Mubanga et al., 2023), explored theoretical centralized and decentralised scenarios for a post-COVID recovery, the IRP provides the formal, government-led investment framework required to achieve these economic goals.

The IRP and Nyambe-Mubanga et al. (2023) provide important insights into possible energy system pathways; however, they offer limited understanding of the broader macroeconomic implications of such large-scale investments. It is particularly important to estimate the economy-wide effects on GDP, sectoral output, labour, household incomes, income distribution and the trade balance that arise from the IRP investments, given that the IRP is a government-led investment programme. To achieve this, we propose a multiplier analysis using a Social Accounting Matrix (SAM). This analysis evaluates how the scale and composition of IRP-related investments may transmit through the wider economy, generating indirect and induced economic effects beyond the power sector itself (i.e. the direct effect). The SAM captures the economy-wide linkages between the energy sector and other productive sectors, institutions, and household groups, thereby providing insights into how energy infrastructure investments may influence economic activity and income distribution. This work builds on the previous macroeconomic analysis of Nyambe-Mubanga et al. (2023) scenarios, in Tembo & Pye (2024).

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 focuses on the methodological approach. The first sub-section describes the use of Social Accounting Matrices and associated multiplier analysis for estimating the wider economic impacts of investment. This is followed by a sub-section that outlines the application of this approach in the Zambian context, including the development of an extended Zambian SAM designed to capture energy sector linkages and the construction of investment scenarios based on the IRP. It then concludes with a sub-section that highlights model assumptions, closure rules and limitations. Section 3 presents and discusses the results of the multiplier analysis, focusing on the economy-wide and distributional impacts of IRP investment. Section 4 offers concluding remarks.

Methodological Approach

This work focuses on the economic implications of Zambia's Integrated Resource Plan (IRP) developed by CIGZambia and published in 2024 by the Ministry of Energy (MoE, 2024). The IRP is a 30-year investment plan focusing on electricity generation, transmission and distribution infrastructure. Over this time horizon, the plan proposes a total of US\$11.6 billion and US\$31.0 billion by 2030 and 2050 respectively. The magnitude of these investments notwithstanding, there has not been any analysis to provide insights on the broader economic implications resulting from these investments. In this analysis, we aim to fill this gap by using a Social Accounting Matrix (SAM)

multiplier model through the estimation of macroeconomic impacts of these proposed IRP investments. This multiplier analysis will provide easy-to-derive estimates of broader economic impacts, that complement detailed techno-economic approaches of the energy sector.

SAM and associated Multiplier Analysis

Social Accounting Matrix (SAM)

A Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) is a comprehensive and economy-wide database recording data on transactions between economic agents in a certain economy during a certain period of time, typically a year. The SAM covers two main areas: it provides data for economic modelling (multi-sectoral linear models or the more complex Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) Models) and it shows a complete but intuitive snapshot of the structure of the economy (Mainar-Causepe et al., 2018). Historically, the idea of a SAM can be traced to Stone (1947), whose pioneering work on social accounting includes most of the conventions which would later be adopted by economic and statistical organisations. The idea was then formalised by Pyatt & Thorbecke (1976) who facilitated its use as a formal framework for economic analysis and planning.

At the core of a SAM is the economic concept of circular flow of income. The circular flow (see Figure 1 below) captures the generation of income by activities in producing commodities, the mapping of these income payments to factors of production of various kinds, the distribution of factor and non-factor income to households, and the subsequent spending of income by households on commodities. These patterns of payments are manifested in the structure of the SAM, and are also modelled analogously to the input structure of activities in an input-output model based only on inter-industry transactions.

Understanding the socioeconomic outcomes resulting from energy investments and other related policy and investment options is essential for policymakers. Tools such as the SAM therefore become essential in quantifying, qualifying and projecting the socioeconomic outcomes of policy options. Thus, the SAM is well suited for analysing macroeconomic impacts, such as employment and income distribution. The SAM makes it possible to analyse direct, indirect and induced job effects at the sector level. Because it is based on national accounts and data collected at the country level, it is transparent, accessible and relatively easy to build and use (ILO, 2017). In addition, the SAM is useful for policy formulation and evaluation due to its socioeconomic coverage.

Figure 1: Circular flow of income (Cooper and John, 2012)

Table 1 shows the structure of a basic SAM which is laid out as a square matrix in which each transaction or account has its own row and column. The payments are listed in columns, and receipts are recorded in rows. The sum of all expenditures by a given account must equal the total sum of receipts or income for the corresponding account.

Table 1: Basic SAM structure

	Production (P)	Factors (F)	Households (HH)	Govt (G)	Savings/ Invest (S/I)	Row	Total
P	Intermed. Inputs		Private consumption	Gov. consumption	Investment	Export	Demand
F	Value added					Factor inc. from ROW	Factor income
HH		Factor inc. to HH	Inter HH Transfers	Transfers to HH		Transfer to HH	HH income
G	Prod., sales, export, VAT	Factor inc. to G, factor taxes	Transfers to G, direct			Transfer to G	G income
S/I			HH savings	Gov. savings		Foreign savings	Savings
Row	Imports	Factor inc. to ROW		Gov. transfers to ROW			Foreign exch. outflow
Total	Supply expend.	Factor expend	HH expend	Gov. expend.	Investment	Foreign exch. inflow	

Source: Adapted from Peterson (2003)

Typically, a SAM has six (6) basic groups of accounts: activities and/or commodities, production (factors), (private) institutions – households and corporations/enterprises, government (public institutions), (combined) capital accounts, accounts for the rest of the world (as shown in Table 1). These accounts are described further in Box 1.

Box 1. Three features of the SAM

The six components of the SAM can be summed up into three broad categories as presented by Breisinger et al., (2009). The first category is that of “activities” and “commodities.” Activities are the entities that produce goods and services, and commodities are those goods and services produced by activities. Activities produce goods and services by combining the factors of production with intermediate inputs. This is shown in the activity column of the SAM, where activities pay for the wages, rents, and profits they generate during the production process (value-added). Essentially, this is a payment from activities to factors, and so the value-added entry in the SAM appears in the activity column and the factor row. Likewise, intermediate demand is a payment from activities to commodities and so adding together value-added and intermediate demand gives gross output. Commodities are either supplied domestically or imported. Indirect sales taxes and import tariffs are paid on these commodities and this means that the values in the commodity accounts are measured at market prices.

The second broad category is that of domestic institutions. It is worth noting that a SAM is different from an input-output matrix (or table) because it not only traces the income and expenditure flows of activities and commodities, but it also contains complete information on different institutional accounts, such as households and the government. Households are usually the ultimate owners of the factors of production, and so they receive the incomes earned by factors during the production process. They also receive transfer payments from the government, such as social security and pensions, and from the rest of the world

(remittances received from family members working abroad). It then follows that households pay taxes directly to the government and purchase commodities. The remaining income is then saved (or dis-saved if expenditures exceed incomes). It is worth noting that information in household accounts is usually drawn from national accounts and household surveys from the country's statistics bureau. The government receives transfer payments from the rest of the world (such as foreign grants and development assistance). This is added to all of the different tax incomes to determine total government revenues. These revenues are used by the government to pay for recurrent consumption spending and transfers to households. From the difference between total revenues and expenditures we then have a fiscal surplus (or deficit, if expenditures exceed revenues).

The third broad category is that of savings, investment and foreign accounts. According to the ex-post accounting identity, investment or gross capital formation, which includes changes in stocks or inventories, must equal total savings. The difference between total domestic savings and total investment demand is total capital inflows from abroad, or what is called the current account balance. This is also equal to the difference between foreign exchange receipts (exports and foreign transfers received) and expenditures (imports and government transfers to foreigners). Information on the current account (or rest of the world) is drawn from the balance of payments, which is usually published by a country's central bank.

In a broad sense, the SAM is used to simulate exogenous demand-side shocks such as changes in export demand, government spending, or investment demand. In this analysis, we are considering the 'shock' as being the investments associated with the IRP. The impacts of these shocks can have both direct and indirect effects on the economy. Direct effects (or linkages) are those pertaining to the sector that is directly affected by the shock. Indirect effects can, in turn, be separated into production and consumption linkages. Adding up all direct and indirect linkages leads to a measure of the shock's multiplier effect, or how much a direct effect is amplified or multiplied by indirect linkage effects (Breisinger et al., 2009).

Production linkages which are determined by sectors' production technologies can be split into forward and backward linkages. Backward linkages are defined as the demands for additional inputs used by producers to supply additional goods or services whereas forward production linkages account for the increased supply of inputs to upstream industries. Consequently, stronger forward and backward linkages lead to larger multipliers. It is also worth noting that SAM multipliers capture the consumption linkages, which arise when an expansion of production generates additional incomes for factors and households, which are then used to purchase goods and services. As such, SAM multipliers tend to be larger than input-output multipliers because they capture both production and consumption/income linkages (Breisinger et al., 2009).

To illustrate the effects of these different linkages, let's consider the share of imported goods and services in households' consumption demand. If households consume domestically produced goods, then as household incomes increase, this will benefit domestic producers and the circular flow of income will lead to further rounds of indirect linkage effects. Yet, if households demand imported goods, then it is foreign producers who benefit. Consequently, the indirect linkage effects will be smaller. Therefore, import demand is a leakage from the circular flow of income. In the same way, when the government taxes income earned on factors of production, it limits how much of the returns to production are earned to households, and so reduces consumption linkages. Eventually, these kinds of leakages make the effects slow down more quickly and reduce the total multiplier effect (Breisinger et al., 2009).

An overview of multiplier analysis approaches

There are two types of multipliers that can be developed, namely an unconstrained multiplier and a constrained multiplier. The difference between the two lies in the assumptions made about resources in the economy. Under the unconstrained multiplier, it is assumed that prices are fixed and that any changes in demand will lead to changes in physical output rather than prices. This in turn requires an additional assumption that the economy's factor resources are unlimited or unconstrained, so that any increase in demand can be matched by an increase in supply. The model also assumes that all

structural relationships between sectors and households in the economy are unaffected by exogenous changes in demand. Using matrix algebra, a multiplier is then developed which shows that when exogenous demand increases, after taking all rounds of direct and indirect linkage effects into account, there is a final increase in total demand.

The constrained multiplier drops the assumption that sectors' supply responses are unconstrained by fixing the level of output in certain sectors. This requires some adjustments to the multiplier formula to derive a constrained multiplier model. The equation for the constrained multiplier tells us that an exogenous increase in demand for the unconstrained sectors leads to a final increase in total demand for these sectors, including all of the forward and backward linkages. However, for the sectors with constrained supply, it is the net exports that decline while imports increase to replace the shortfall in domestic production. Because exports are now included inside exogenous demand, the equations solve for the impact of a change in demand on net exports, rather than the other way around (Breisinger et al., 2009).

Multiplier analysis can provide a useful simplified assessment, notably in countries where dynamic economy-wide models, such as Computable General Equilibrium (CGE) models, are not available. For such models, fairly advanced analytical skills and time are required to undertake economy-wide investigations. Further, many people may not easily understand and interpret economy-wide models.

There are many examples of multiplier analysis that have focused on a developing country context and explored the impact of investment in the energy sector. Milani et al. (2020) used such an analysis to assess the impact of a 300 MW solar thermal programme in Brazil on jobs, incomes and economic output. Vasconcellos and Caiado Couto (2021) estimated the economic impacts of investment in wind generation in North East Brazil. Garrett-Peltier (2017) used input-output analysis to determine the relative job creation associated with investment in renewables versus fossil fuels, finding that investment in renewables leads to much larger employment multipliers. For a multiplier analysis, either the focus is on a specific project investment or investment profiles can be generated by other modelling - and fed into the SAM. A useful example of this approach is documented for Tunisia, in Howells et al. (2021). This paper derives multipliers from a SAM multiplier model and uses investments from the IRP model to assess economic impacts, notably on GDP and household income.

While SAM multipliers provide detailed analysis about the linkages, income distribution etc., there are some important limitations. Firstly, in many cases certain accounts such as factors and households might be too aggregated to understand any relationships. For example, economy-wide models using the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP), have historically assumed one type of household for the country and region. However, households differ by urban or rural setup. In addition, households differ by income levels and sources of income. Some households depend on wages and self-employment while others subsist on transfers and remittances. As such, their use of one household type in economy wide models can be misleading (Sigwele, 2007).

Secondly, data are required from national accounts, household and income surveys as well as farm or agricultural surveys. In many countries these data may not be available at the same time in order for one to conduct a SAM-based analysis. Finally, such analyses are by their nature static, exploring a shock at a single point in time. This means that any policy shocks that flow through the SAM do not result in price feedback and a revised SAM. The structure of the economy is not changed in the subsequent period that would be needed to allow for a recursive analysis.

The use of a Zambian SAM to develop a multiplier analysis

The development of a Zambian SAM to assess investments in the energy sector was first published in Tembo & Pye (2024) but is summarised again in this document, to ensure completeness.

Zambian 2019 SAM and extension

Zambia's 2019 SAM was developed by the International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), with a base year of 2019 (Pauw et al., 2021).¹ The SAM has three macroeconomic accounts: government balance, current account, and savings-investment macroeconomic accounts. It is a fairly well disaggregated SAM, including agricultural sector activities (capturing all major crops and livestock) and households by region (rural-urban split). In total, it has 42 economic activities, a total of 10 household types and a total of three labour types. However, this SAM only has one electricity activity and commodity type. Therefore, it is important to make some extensions to this SAM.

With the base SAM (Pauw et al., 2021) already in place, the starting point of the extension was to split three sectors (mine, chem and elec) into 'mining' (mine), 'chemicals and petroleum' (chem), and 'electricity, gas and steam' (elec) activity and commodity sectors - into more detail to give a total of sixteen sectors. The correspondence between the old and new sectors are shown in Table 2. The intention was to remain entirely consistent with the original IFPRI SAM and split the three sectors using other data, therefore, it should be to simply aggregate the new sectors, created and detailed in this document, together to create the original SAM.

The main other data sources used to undertake the disaggregation are electricity generation statistics from Zesco Limited Power (ZESCO, 2022) and the Global Trade Analysis Project (GTAP 10) database (Aguar et al. 2019). The former provided us with the electricity generation by technology in 2019 for Zambia, the base year of the IFPRI SAM. The latter, the GTAP-Power database, provided us with a SAM for Zambia for 2014 which does have greater detail on the sectors of interest here. Therefore, it was possible to use the GTAP database to inform the cost structure in our disaggregation. For the sake of simplicity, we do not disaggregate between base load and peak electricity generating technologies and therefore when using GTAP-Power data these are aggregated together and considered as one (e.g., in GTAP-Power there are both baseload and peak electricity generation from gas and oil, these are combined for our database). Details of this disaggregation activity can be found in Tembo & Pye (2024).

Table 2: Mapping of old sectors to new sectors

IFPRI original sector	Description	New sectors	Description
mine	Mining	coal	Mining of coal
		oil	Oil extraction
		gas	Extraction of gas
		miner	All other mining including metals, minerals etc.
chem	Chemicals and petroleum	petrol	Petroleum, coal products
		chem	Chemical products
elec	Electricity, gas and water	edist	Electricity transmission and distribution
		enucl	Electricity from nuclear energy
		ecoal	Electricity from coal power
		ewind	Electricity from wind power
		eothe	Electricity from other power sources
		egas	Electricity from gas
		ehydro	Electricity from hydro power
		eoil	Electricity from oil

¹ The International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI) has developed two Social Accounting Matrices (SAM) in quick succession, with base years of 2019 (Pauw et al., 2021) and 2021 (Pauw et al., 2022).

		esolar	Electricity from solar power
		gdist	Gas distribution and transmission

Zambian Multiplier Model

The Zambian multiplier model is based on the framework provided in IFPRI's Social Accounting Matrices and Multiplier Analysis: An Introduction with Exercises (Breisinger et al., 2009), which is itself based on the Leontief model (see Miller and Blair (2009) for a detailed discourse on the Leontief model).

Given that a SAM contains activities among various economic agents of a given economy, below is a summary derivation of SAM multiplier model for a two-sector economy:

Total demand Z is expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} Z_1 &= a_{11}X_1 + a_{12}X_2 + c_1Y + E_1 \\ Z_2 &= a_{21}X_1 + a_{22}X_2 + c_2Y + E_2 \end{aligned} \quad \text{Eqn (1)}$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned} X_i &= b_i * Z_i && \text{is domestic production,} \\ Y &= v_i * X_i && \text{is household income, and} \\ E_i &&& \text{is exogenous demand.} \end{aligned}$$

After substituting and separating endogenous variables from exogenous variables, equation (1) can be rewritten in matrix form as

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 - a_{11}b_1 - c_1v_1b_1 & -a_{12}b_2 - c_1v_2b_2 \\ -a_{21}b_1 - c_2v_1b_1 & 1 - a_{22}b_2 - c_2v_2b_2 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} Z_1 \\ Z_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} E_1 \\ E_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eqn(2)}$$

After rearranging equation (2), we get an unconstrained multiplier equation

$$Z = (I - M)^{-1} * E \quad \text{Eqn(3)}$$

Where:

$$\begin{aligned} Z &&& \text{is the total demand vector,} \\ (I - M)^{-1} &&& \text{is the multiplier matrix (this takes into account both the direct and indirect multiplier effects), and} \\ E &&& \text{is the exogenous demand vector.} \end{aligned}$$

Under the constrained model, unconstrained sectors that can change their production levels are distinguished from those that cannot (constrained sectors). And for sectors that cannot change their production levels, there will be endogenous imports substitution. Thus, under the constrained model, equation (3) is rewritten as

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 - a_{11}b_1 - c_1v_1b_1 & 0 \\ -a_{21}b_1 - c_2v_1b_1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} Z_1 \\ E_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & a_{12}b_2 + c_1v_2b_2 \\ 0 & -1 + a_{22}b_2 + c_2v_2b_2 \end{pmatrix} * \begin{pmatrix} E_1 \\ Z_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eqn(4)}$$

After substituting for $(I - M^*)$ and B , we get a constrained multiplier equation

$$\begin{pmatrix} Z_1 \\ E_2 \end{pmatrix} = (I - M^*)^{-1} * B * \begin{pmatrix} E_1 \\ Z_2 \end{pmatrix} \quad \text{Eqn(5)}$$

Where:

$(I - M^*)^{-1}$ is the adjusted multiplier matrix (this takes into account both the forward and backward linkages), and

B is a term which acts as one of constraining factors,

Due to limited supply from the constrained sectors, it implies that as demand grows in unconstrained sectors, net exports in the constrained sectors reduce. This reduction acts as a limiting factor to the overall economic growth of an economy i.e. the strength of the overall multiplier effect.

Energy investments from the IRP

Table 3 below shows the accumulated investment up to 2050 (a total USD25 billion) and the yearly averages of capital investment (in USD millions) for the IRP investment profiles broken down technology type (generation and transmission technologies).

Table 3: IRP projected capital investment by power technology (MoE, 2024)

Generation Technology	Generation Investments (Million USD)	
	2022 -2050	Average
Hydro Storage	0	0.00
Hydro (Run-of-River)	6,545	233.8
Thermal - Steam (Coal/other fuels)	1,930	68.9
Geothermal	1,584	56.6
Biomass	769	27.5
Solar PV	4,797	171.3
Wind	7,206	257.4
Nuclear	0	0.00
Solar CSP	0	0.00
Imports & Infr.	2,386	85.2
Total Investment	25,217.4	900.6

Model assumptions and closure rules

This model is implemented as a linear, demand-driven system, where sectoral outputs (endogenously determined) respond to exogenous changes (IRP investments) in final demand. IRP investment shocks are introduced as injections into the economy, and their effects are traced through inter-sectoral linkages using a fixed-coefficient production structure.

The model utilises the Keynesian closure rule to assess the macroeconomic impact of these exogenous investments and assumes that the Zambian economy operates with idle capacity. This implies that the new investment will be accommodated without needing to re-employ capacity nor adjust prices (i.e. prices are fixed). Such a closure rule allows for output to expand in response to increased demand without encountering binding constraints i.e. unconstrained model.

To estimate the impacts of the IRP investments, say in the hydropower sector, the inter-sectoral (forward and backward) linkages in the SAM are utilised to trace the direct and indirect effects of such an investment. Investments in the hydropower sector necessitate inputs from manufacturing and services, creating a ripple effect that propagates across the entire supply chain. Further, because more labour and capital are employed, total household income will increase, which in turn results in increased consumption from households leading to increased sectoral outputs and GDP growth.

While the SAM multiplier framework provides useful insights into economy-wide linkages, it has several limitations:

- It does not capture price adjustments, substitution effects, or behavioural responses to relative price changes
- It assumes unlimited factor supply, which may overstate impacts in the presence of binding constraints
- It does not explicitly model dynamic effects, such as productivity changes or technological progress

Based on the limitations outlined above, it is important that the model results are interpreted as indicative magnitude of short-run economic impacts, rather than precise forecasts and long-run impacts.

Results & Discussion

This section presents the results and provides a discussion of the impact analysis using the above SAM framework. It evaluates how energy sector investments defined in the IRP propagate through the broader economy by capturing the interlinkages between production activities, factors of production, households, government, and the external sector. The analysis focuses on the technology-specific impacts derived from the IRP's investment profile.

The technology-specific assessment evaluates the downstream effects of capital injections into various energy projects, as detailed in the investment schedule (Table 3 above). The analytical approach utilises the multiplier framework to quantify the resulting shocks on four critical macroeconomic indicators: Gross Domestic Product (GDP), total economic output, import demand (leakage) and aggregate household income. By isolating these variables, the analysis provides a comprehensive view of how energy-sector infrastructure serves as a driver for value-added generation and domestic industrialisation within the Zambian economy.

Impact of sectoral constraints and macroeconomic sensitivity

In Tembo & Pye (2024), we presented some key findings of how the SAM framework behaves under both constrained and unconstrained model assumptions. For completeness of this analysis, we present a summary of how the model would behave under constrained assumptions, as we note that multiplier effects (on which this paper is based) are likely overstated since they ignore potential supply-side constraints during a demand shock (Haggblad et al., 1991) i.e. here we use an unconstrained version of the model.

Tables 8a through 8d (of Tembo & Pye (2024)) give the magnitude and associated uncertainty of economic impacts when specific activities in the economy are constrained. By comparing constrained simulations to an unconstrained baseline (under a scenario where final demand for all other commodities increases by K1 billion) the results quantify the systemic sensitivity of the Zambian economy to sectoral bottlenecks.

The analysis of model behaviour identifies the Service sector as the most critical pivot in the national economy. Constraining this sector leads to profound declines in all key indicators: GDP contracts by approximately 75% (with an uncertainty of 0.454 standard deviation (std.dev)), while total output falls by 55% (0.316 std.dev). Notably, household income exhibits the highest sensitivity, with a contraction of 106% (0.682 std.dev), suggesting that household livelihoods are inextricably linked to service-sector activity. These findings underscore the intensive inter-sectoral linkages inherent in the service sector and implies that mitigating policy, regulatory or infrastructural barriers to service sector growth is a prerequisite for broader economic stability.

Within the energy landscape, hydropower represents both the most impactful (GDP contracts by approximately 7.6%) and the most volatile (with an uncertainty of 0.145 (std.dev)) technology, in terms of multiplier effects. While it yields the largest multipliers, it also introduces the highest level of uncertainty across GDP, Income, and Output. Given that Zambia’s energy portfolio is hydropower-dominated and increasingly susceptible to climate-induced hydrological variability, this volatility poses a significant risk to macroeconomic resilience. Consequently, the results provide a strong empirical basis for diversifying the generation mix beyond hydropower to insulate the socioeconomic framework from climate shocks and ensure a more stable growth trajectory.

The macroeconomic implications of energy investments

Table 4 below summarises the macroeconomic impacts of specific energy sector investments as given in Table 3 above. As shown in Table 3, the average yearly IRP capital investment from 2022 to 2050 is US\$900 million. The results suggest that every unit of investment in the energy sector yields an output multiplier of 1.89 and a GDP multiplier of 1.10.² These results indicate that every unit of capital injected into the energy sector generates nearly double its value in gross output, while simultaneously expanding national value-added (GDP) by 10 percent beyond the initial investment.

Table 4: Macroeconomic impacts of specific energy sector capital investments

Variable	IRP
GDP	995
Income	670
Output	1,700
total demand	2,427
GDP / Investment	1.1
Income / Investment	0.74
Output / Investment	1.89
Total Demand / Investment	2.69

These investments result in an import multiplier of approximately 0.23. This implies that 23% of each unit of IRP investment leaks abroad through imported goods and services. While the investments

² In simple terms, output measures the total value of all transactions across the production chain (including intermediate inputs), whereas GDP measures only the value added at each stage, representing the net new wealth generated in the economy.

generate substantial domestic output gains (retaining nearly 77% of the initial capital injection domestically) its foreign exchange implications are non-trivial. This underscores the importance of strengthening domestic supply chains to further maximise local value capture and also requires careful management of foreign currency reserves. Further, the import propensity is approximately 12.4%, indicating that over 87% of the economic expansion induced by the IRP investment is retained within the domestic economy. This level of internal absorption reflects robust backward linkages and successfully contained foreign exchange leakage, highlighting the potential benefits of these investments.

These IRP investments generate an income multiplier of approximately 0.74, implying that nearly three-quarters of the initial capital injection is successfully transmitted into households (i.e. labour and capital factor incomes). While this indicates strong aggregate labour and capital income effects, the distribution is markedly urban-centric, with urban households capturing 82.8% (\$555 million to urban area vs \$115 million to rural area) of these gains. This suggests that while the IRP offers broad-based national benefits, additional policy measures may be required to deepen the economic participation of rural communities in the energy supply chain.

At a disaggregated level, transmission of these income gains is characterised by significant socioeconomic concentration: gains are captured by the highest urban income bracket (*hhd_r5*). This reflects a structural skew toward households that already possess significant capital assets and specialised skills. By contrast, the lowest urban quintiles (*hhd_u1* and *hhd_u2*) receive minimal benefits, with income increases of only US\$1.5 million and US\$5.9 million, respectively. This pattern suggests that low-skilled urban workers face barriers to participation in the formal energy supply chain.

Although the absolute gains in rural areas are lower than those in urban areas, the rural quintiles exhibit a markedly different distributional profile. The benefits are more progressively distributed across the quintiles. Income increases incrementally from US\$9.7 million in the lowest rural quintile (*hhd_r1*) to US\$33.3 million in the highest (*hhd_r5*). This more balanced distribution suggests that the impact is driven by broader indirect multipliers such as increased demand for agricultural commodities rather than the concentrated technical labour demand and capital assets among urban quintiles.

On the whole, this analysis suggests that IRP investments (like many other infrastructure-led growth) may not translate to inclusive economic growth. To enhance inclusivity, several policy interventions may be required to strengthen rural production linkages, promote productive-use electrification, and target skills development and fiscal transfers toward rural communities and lower quintiles of urban households.

Concluding Remarks

The Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) framework provides a consistent and robust approach for conducting macroeconomic analysis at the national or regional level for a given year. By capturing the interlinkages between production activities, institutions, factors of production, and the external sector, the SAM framework offers means for evaluating the economy-wide implications of policy interventions. In this context, it serves as an important analytical tool for assessing energy investments, climate mitigation strategies, and broader socioeconomic development plans that the Zambian Government may consider.

In this study, the SAM-based analysis highlights key structural characteristics of the Zambian economy. Particularly, economic activities that may act as potential bottlenecks if adequate policy and institutional environments are not established are identified. The analysis demonstrates the critical role of the services sector in sustaining economic activity, as well as the structural importance of hydropower within the national energy system.

The assessment of IRP investments under the unconstrained model further demonstrates the strong macroeconomic benefits of energy sector investments. The results indicate that each unit of capital investment in the energy sector generates at least a 1.10 increase in GDP, while also producing significant positive impacts on total output, aggregate household income, and overall economic demand. These findings confirm that energy infrastructure investments have substantial multiplier effects and can act as an important driver of economic expansion in Zambia.

However, the analysis also reveals that the benefits of these investments are not evenly distributed across the economy. Based on the current structure of the Zambian economy, the results suggest that the IRP, in its present form, may not fully achieve its intended inclusive growth objectives. The distributional results indicate that economic gains are likely to be concentrated in sectors and households that are already well integrated into formal economic activities, while rural households and urban lower-income groups capture a smaller share of the benefits.

These findings suggest that while expanding energy investments under the IRP should remain a priority, complementary policy measures are essential to ensure that the resulting growth is broad-based and inclusive. This requires a combination of sound macroeconomic management (particularly exchange rate stability to manage import leakages) and targeted structural interventions that enhance domestic value capture. Strengthening local supply chains, promoting local content, and increasing participation of domestic firms can help reduce the concentration of benefits among higher-income urban groups. At the same time, integrating energy investments with productive-use initiatives such as agro-processing, irrigation, and cold storage can translate electricity access into income generation, especially in rural areas. Expanding decentralised energy systems, alongside investments in skills development, SME financing, and rural enterprise support, will further enable wider participation in energy value chains. Collectively, these measures can shift the IRP from a predominantly urban, capital-intensive growth model toward a more inclusive and resilient pathway for industrialisation and poverty reduction.

Overall, the analysis underscores the critical role of energy infrastructure in supporting Zambia's economic development. At the same time, it highlights the importance of aligning energy investments with broader structural and social policies to ensure that the gains from energy sector expansion translate into sustainable, resilient, and inclusive economic growth.

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